

 [VIDEO: How to use this page](#)

 Create snapshot of instruments

Last snapshot: 2023-08-18 14:34

This page allows you to build and customize your data collection instruments one field at a time. You may add new fields or edit existing ones. New fields may be added by clicking the **Add Field** buttons. You can begin editing an existing field by clicking on the **Delete** icon. To reorder the fields, simply **drag and drop** a field to a different position within the form below. NOTE: While in development status, all field changes will take effect immediately in real time.

[Return to list of instruments](#)

[Next instrument >>](#)

Current instrument: **IMPRECISION ASSESSMENT**

[Preview instrument](#)

 Variable: record_id

Record ID

NOTE: The field above is the record ID field and thus cannot be deleted or moved. It can only be edited.

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

 Variable: link_to_covidence

METSA covidence

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

 Variable: studconc_header_grade

GRADE in publication

Add Field

Add Matrix of Fields

Import from Field Bank

Variable: imprecision_reviewer

NEW QUESTION

Who reviewed for GRADE imprecision?

- JBM
- JPS
- BK
- CGR
- CL
- CM
- EBP
- JHPR
- JHS
- MA
- MHO
- SHH
- VW
- ZYL
- Not assigned

Add Field

Add Matrix of Fields

Import from Field Bank

Variable: studcon_gradeyn

DON'T REVIEW

Was GRADE used for one or more outcomes to which TSA was applied?

- Yes, one
- Yes, more than one
- No

GRADE = Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluations

(including outcomes where TSA wasn't performed due to lack of data)

Add Field

Add Matrix of Fields

Import from Field Bank

Variable: studcon_gradingnum Branching logic: [studcon_gradeyn]=2

DON'T REVIEW

How many outcomes were GRADE'd AND analyzed with TSA?

(including outcomes where TSA wasn't performed due to lack of data)

Add Field

Add Matrix of Fields

Import from Field Bank

Variable: studcon_gradetxt Branching logic: [studcon_gradeyn]<>0

DON'T REVIEW

HIDDEN_in_1.1

Describe to which outcome(s) GRADE was applied

Describe only outcomes to which TSA was applied. You noted, that the following outcomes were not analyzed: [outc_tsa_miss]

Add Field

Add Matrix of Fields

Import from Field Bank

Variable: studcon_grades

Branching logic: [studcon_gradeyn]<>0

Contains embedded fields

DON'T REVIEW

To which outcome(s) were GRADE applied?

<p>Primary</p>	<p>{studcon_prim_grade_1} {studcon_prim_grade_2} {studcon_prim_grade_3} {studcon_prim_grade_4}{studcon_prim_grade_5}{studcon_prim_grade_6} {studcon_prim_grade_7}{studcon_prim_grade_8}{studcon_prim_grade_9} {studcon_prim_grade_10}{studcon_prim_grade_11}{studcon_prim_grade_12} {studcon_prim_grade_13}{studcon_prim_grade_14}{studcon_prim_grade_15} {studcon_prim_grade_16}{studcon_prim_grade_17}{studcon_prim_grade_18} {studcon_prim_grade_19}{studcon_prim_grade_20}For outcomes not listed: {studcon_prim_grade_comment}</p>
<p>Secondary</p>	<p>{studcon_sec_grade_1}{studcon_sec_grade_2}{studcon_sec_grade_3} {studcon_sec_grade_4}{studcon_sec_grade_5}{studcon_sec_grade_6} {studcon_sec_grade_7}{studcon_sec_grade_8}{studcon_sec_grade_9} {studcon_sec_grade_10}{studcon_sec_grade_11}{studcon_sec_grade_12} {studcon_sec_grade_13}{studcon_sec_grade_14}{studcon_sec_grade_15} {studcon_sec_grade_16}{studcon_sec_grade_17}{studcon_sec_grade_18} {studcon_sec_grade_19}{studcon_sec_grade_20}For outcomes not listed: {studcon_sec_grade_comment}</p>
<p>Exploratory</p>	<p>{studcon_exp_grade_1}{studcon_exp_grade_2}{studcon_exp_grade_3} {studcon_exp_grade_4}{studcon_exp_grade_5}{studcon_exp_grade_6} {studcon_exp_grade_7}{studcon_exp_grade_8}{studcon_exp_grade_9} {studcon_exp_grade_10} {studcon_exp_grade_11}{studcon_exp_grade_12}{studcon_exp_grade_13} {studcon_exp_grade_14}{studcon_exp_grade_15}{studcon_exp_grade_16} {studcon_exp_grade_17}{studcon_exp_grade_18}{studcon_exp_grade_19} {studcon_exp_grade_20}For outcomes not listed: {studcon_exp_grade_comment}</p>

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_grade_comment

Do you have any further comments on the application of GRADE?

[For new entries, keep the existing comment and add new comment like: "JBM: Jadadada"]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_comment

Branching logic: [outc_prim_comment] <> 0

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was GRADE applied to primary outcomes > 20?

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_comment

Branching logic: [outc_sec_comment] <> 0

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was GRADE applied to secondary outcomes > 20?

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_comment

Branching logic: [outc_exp_comment] <> 0

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was GRADE applied to exploratory outcomes > 20?

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: re100aa_2_vjbm *Branching logic: [studcon_gradeyn]=2*

DON'T REVIEW

How were the outcomes GRADE'd?

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Very low

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_1 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>0*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_prim_1]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_2 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>1*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_prim_2]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_3 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>2*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_prim_3]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_4 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>3*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_prim_4]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_5 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>4*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_prim_5]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_6 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>5*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_prim_6]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_7 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>6*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_prim_7]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_8 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>7*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_prim_8]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_9 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>8*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_prim_9]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_10 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>9*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_prim_10]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_11 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>10*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_prim_11]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_12 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>11*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_prim_12]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_13 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>12*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_prim_13]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_14 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>13*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_prim_14]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_15 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>14*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_prim_15]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_16 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>15*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_prim_16]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_17 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>16*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_prim_17]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_18 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>17*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_prim_18]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_19 *Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>18*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_prim_19]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_prim_grade_20 Branching logic: [outc_primnum]>19

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_prim_20]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_1 Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>0

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_sec_1]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_2 Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>1

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_sec_2]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_3 Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>2

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_sec_3]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_4 Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>3

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_sec_4]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_5 Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>4

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_sec_5]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_6 Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>5

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_sec_6]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_7 *Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>6*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_sec_7]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_8 *Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>7*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_sec_8]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_9 *Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>8*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_sec_9]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_10 *Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>9*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_sec_10]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_11 *Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>10*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_sec_11]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_12 *Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>11*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_sec_12]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_13 *Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>12*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_sec_13]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_14 *Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>13*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_sec_14]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_15 *Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>14*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_sec_15]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_16 *Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>15*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_sec_16]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_17 *Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>16*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_sec_17]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_18 *Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>17*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_sec_18]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_19 *Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>18*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_sec_19]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_sec_grade_20 *Branching logic: [outc_secnum]>19*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_sec_20]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_1 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>0*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_exp_1]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_2 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>1*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_exp_2]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_3 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>2*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_exp_3]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_4 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>3*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_exp_4]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_5 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>4*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_exp_5]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_6 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>5*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_exp_6]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_7 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>6*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied? [outc_exp_7]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_8 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>7*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_exp_8]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_9 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>8*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_exp_9]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_10 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>9*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_exp_10]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_11 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>10*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_exp_11]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_12 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>11*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_exp_12]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_13 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>12*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_exp_13]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_14 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>13*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_exp_14]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_15 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>14*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_exp_15]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_16 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>15*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_exp_16]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_17 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>16*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_exp_17]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_18 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>17*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_exp_18]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_19 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>18*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_exp_19]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_exp_grade_20 *Branching logic: [outc_expnum]>19*

Field is embedded elsewhere on page

Was grade applied?

[outc_exp_20]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_grading Branching logic: [studcon_gradeyn]=1

DON'T REVIEW

How was the outcome GRADE'd?

HIDDEN_in_1.1

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Very low

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_gradedown

Were the downgrade methods for imprecision described
[AMENDMENT: in any detail, e.g., when authors state "we downgrade imprecision one or two levels", you should note "No". If authors state any form of "we downgrade imprecision by using [any method]", you should note "Yes".]?

- Yes
- No

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_gradedownwhere Branching logic: [studcon_gradedown]=1

NEW QUESTION

Where were the methods described?

- Methods section
- Results section
- Supplement
- GRADE/results table
- Other

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_gradedownwhere_txt Branching logic: [studcon_gradedownwhere(99)] = 1

NEW QUESTION

Where were methods described?

Add Field Add Matrix of Fields Import from Field Bank

Variable: studcon_gradedownhow Branching logic: [studcon_gradedown]=1

Which parameters influenced [EDIT: methods were used for] the grading of imprecision in GRADE?

- Imprecision downgraded 2 levels if DARIS < 50%; 1 level if DARIS between 50-100%; 0 levels if DARIS is reached 100% or if the cumulative Z-curve crosses boundaries for futility, benefit or harm
- [DISCONTINUED] - Imprecision downgraded but the cut-offs were different than (1) or not specified (describe below)
- Judgement of the width of conventional 95% CI's [EDIT: conventional GRADE]
- NEW OPTION: Judgment of a calculated OIS (conventional GRADE)
- Imprecision was evaluated using the Trial Sequential adjusted confidence interval [EDIT: conventional GRADE with TSA CI]
- NEW OPTION: Castellini 2018 (which is also Jakobsen 2014)
- NEW OPTION: Jakobsen 2014
- Other
- NEW OPTION: Unclear (only in addition to other options)

Add Field Add Matrix of Fields Import from Field Bank

Variable: studcon_gradedownhowtxt Branching logic: [studcon_gradedownhow(2)] OR [studcon_gradedownhow(3)] OR [stud...

Describe how

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_gradedownunclear *Branching logic: [studcon_gradedownhow(98)] = 1*

NEW QUESTION

Why was it unclear which methods the authors used?

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_gradetsatxt *Branching logic: [studcon_gradetsa]=1*

DON'T REVIEW

Describe how Trial Sequential Analysis influenced GRADE evaluation

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_gradetsa *Branching logic: [studcon_gradedown] = 1*

Did the Trial Sequential Analysis explicitly influence the GRADE assessment?

[AMENDMENT: Yes, when DARIS, TSA CI or Jakobsen options above are used]

- Yes
- No

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_gradedown_ois_yn *Branching logic: [studcon_gradedownhow(7)]=1*

When OIS is used, was it described how the OIS was calculated?

[NEW QUESTION]

- Yes
- No

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_gradedown_ois_txt *Branching logic: [studcon_gradedown_ois_yn] = 1*

How was OIS calculated?

[NEW QUESTION]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_grade_methodyn *Branching logic: [studcon_gradedown] = 1*

NEW QUESTION

In summary, were the methods for downgrading imprecision described in full, i.e., in sufficient detail to allow for reproduction of the assessment?

- Yes
- No

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_gradedownlvltxt *Branching logic: [studcon_gradedownlvl]=99 OR [studcon_gradedownlvl_2(99)]=1*

DON'T REVIEW

Please describe how imprecision was downgraded

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: studcon_gradedownlvl *Branching logic: [studcon_gradeyn]=1*

DON'T REVIEW

How much was imprecision downgraded?

- 1 level
- 2 levels
- Imprecision was not explicitly downgraded
- Other

Add Field Add Matrix of Fields Import from Field Bank

Variable: studcon_gradedownlvl_2 Branching logic: [studcon_gradeyn]=2

DON'T REVIEW

How much was imprecision downgraded?

- 1 level
- 2 levels
- Imprecision was not explicitly downgraded
- Other

Add Field Add Matrix of Fields Import from Field Bank

Variable: gradeplan_header Branching logic: [pa_yn]=1

Planning of GRADE

Add Field Add Matrix of Fields Import from Field Bank

Variable: gradeplan_yn Branching logic: [pa_yn]=1

DON'T REVIEW

Was GRADE assessment planned in the protocol

- Yes
- No

Add Field Add Matrix of Fields Import from Field Bank

Variable: gradeplan_outc Branching logic: [gradeplan_yn]=1

DON'T REVIEW

Did the protocol define which outcomes would undergo a GRADE assessment?

- Yes
- No

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: gradeplan_check Branching logic: [gradeplan_outc]=1

DON'T REVIEW

Was the outcome(s) planned for GRADE assessment the same as was assessed in the study?

Yes

No

GRADE assessment(s) in study:

Only for outcomes to which TSA were applied

[studcon_gradetxt]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: gradeplan_checktxt Branching logic: [gradeplan_check]='0'

DON'T REVIEW

Please describe differences between GRADE plan in protocol and GRADE in study

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: gradeplan_down Branching logic: [gradeplan_yn]=1

Were the downgrade methods for imprecision in GRADE described in the protocol [AMENDMENT: in any detail, e.g., when authors state "we downgrade imprecision one or two levels", you should note "No". If authors state any form of "we downgrade imprecision by using [any method]", you should note "Yes".]?

Yes

No

Add Field Add Matrix of Fields Import from Field Bank

Variable: gradeplan_downwhich Branching logic: [gradeplan_down]=1

Did the protocol describe how imprecision would be downgraded [FOLLOWING TEXT NOT RELEVANT: with the use of Trial Sequential Analysis]?

- Imprecision downgraded 2 levels if DARIS < 50%; 1 level if DARIS between 50-100%; 0 levels if DARIS is reached 100% or if the cumulative Z-curve crosses boundaries for futility, benefit or harm
- [DISCONTINUED] - Imprecision downgraded but the cut-offs were different than (1) or not specified (describe below)
- NEW OPTION IN THIS ITEM: Judgement of the width of conventional 95% CI's (conventional GRADE)
- NEW OPTION: Judgment of a calculated OIS (conventional GRADE)
- Imprecision was evaluated using the Trial Sequential adjusted confidence interval [EDIT: conventional GRADE with TSA CI]
- NEW OPTION: Castellini 2018 (which is also Jakobsen 2014)
- NEW OPTION: Jakobsen 2014
- Other
- NEW OPTION: Unclear
- [DISCONTINUED] No

Add Field Add Matrix of Fields Import from Field Bank

Variable: gradeplan_lim_ben Branching logic: [gradeplan_down] = 1

Were limits for important benefit defined in the protocol?

NEW QUESTION

- Yes
- No

Add Field Add Matrix of Fields Import from Field Bank

Variable: gradeplan_lim_harm Branching logic: [gradeplan_down] = 1

Were limits for important harm defined in the protocol?

NEW QUESTION

- Yes
- No

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: gradeplan_downtxt *Branching logic: [gradeplan_downwhich(99)]=1 OR [gradeplan_downwhich(98)]=1*

Please describe the plan for downgrading imprecision
[FOLLOWING TEXT REMOVED: with the use of TSA]

[AMENDMENT: Please note if you chose "Unclear" or "Other"]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: gradeplan_down_ois_yn *Branching logic: [gradeplan_downwhich(7)]=1*

When OIS is used, was it described how the OIS was calculated?

- Yes
 No

[NEW QUESTION]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: gradeplan_down_ois_txt *Branching logic: [gradeplan_down_ois_yn] = 1*

How was OIS calculated?

[NEW QUESTION]

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

Variable: gradeplan_downtxt2 *Branching logic: [gradeplan_downwhich(0)]=1*

[DISCONTINUED]

Please describe the plan for downgrading imprecision

Add Field

Add Matrix of Fields

Import from Field Bank

Variable: gradeplan_summary *Branching logic: [gradeplan_yn] = 1*

NEW QUESTION

In summary, were the methods for downgrading imprecision described in full, i.e., in sufficient detail to allow for reproduction of the assessment?

- Yes
- No

Add Field

Add Matrix of Fields

Import from Field Bank